

A Lower Bound for the First General Zagreb Index of a Graph

Rao Li

Dept. of mathematical sciences
University of South Carolina Aiken
Aiken, SC 29801
USA

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Abstract

The first general Zagreb index of a graph G is defined as the sum of the α th powers of the vertex degrees of G , where α is a real number such that $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\alpha \neq 1$. In this short note, for $\alpha > 1$, we present a lower upper bound involving the independence number for the first general Zagreb index of a graph.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges, the degree of a vertex v is denoted by $d(v)$. We use δ to denote the minimum degree of G . A set of vertices in a graph G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . For disjoint vertex subsets X and Y of $V(G)$, we use $E(X, Y)$ to denote the set of all the edges in $E(G)$ such that one end vertex of each edge is in X and another end vertex of the edge is in Y . Namely, $E(X, Y) := \{e : e = xy \in E, x \in X, y \in Y\}$.

The first Zagreb index was introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić in [2]. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index is defined as $\sum_{i=1}^n d_G^2(v_i)$. Li and Zheng in [3] further extended the first Zagreb index of a graph and introduced the concept of the first general Zagreb index of a graph. The first general Zagreb index, denoted $M_\alpha(G)$, of a graph G is defined as $\sum_{i=1}^n d_G^\alpha(v_i)$, where α is a real number such that $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\alpha \neq 1$.

In this short note, for $\alpha > 1$, we present a lower upper bound involving the independence number for the first general Zagreb index of a graph. The main result is as follows.

Theorem 1 Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and $\delta \geq 1$. Assume α is a real number such that $\alpha > 1$. Then

$$M_\alpha \geq \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - \beta)^{\alpha-1}}.$$

Equality holds if and only if G is a graph satisfying the following conditions. For any maximum independent set I in G , $d(u) = \delta$ if $u \in I$, $V - I$ is independent and $d(v) = \delta_1 \geq \delta$ if $v \in V - I$, and $e = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1$.

2 A Lemma

The well-known Hölder’s inequality will be used in our proofs for Theorem 1.

Lemma 1 Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k; b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k$ be positive real numbers and $p, q > 1$ be such that $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then

$$\sum_{i=1}^k a_i b_i \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^k a_i^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^k b_i^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

Equality holds if and only if $\frac{a_1^p}{b_1^q} = \frac{a_2^p}{b_2^q} = \dots = \frac{a_k^p}{b_k^q}$.

3 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1 Let I be any maximum independent set in G . Then $|I| = \beta$. Thus

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = |E(I, V - I)| \leq \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v).$$

Since $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) + \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v) = 2e$, we have that

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) \leq e \leq \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v).$$

Set $I = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$. Then we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i) \geq \beta \delta^\alpha.$$

Set $V - I = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-\beta}\}$. Applying Hölder’s inequality with $k = n - \beta$, $a_i = d(v_i) \geq \delta \geq 1$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, (n - \beta)$, $b_i = 1$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, (n - \beta)$, $p = \alpha$, and $q = \frac{p}{p-1} = \frac{\alpha}{\alpha-1}$, we have

$$(n - \beta)^{\frac{\alpha-1}{\alpha}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n-\beta} d^\alpha(v_i) \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \geq \sum_{i=1}^{n-\beta} d(v_i).$$

Namely,

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$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-\beta} d^\alpha(v_i) \geq \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^{n-\beta} d(v_i)\right)^\alpha}{(n-\beta)^{\alpha-1}} \geq \frac{e^\alpha}{(n-\beta)^{\alpha-1}}.$$

Hence

$$M_\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i) + \sum_{i=1}^{n-\beta} d^\alpha(v_i) \geq \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n-\beta)^{\alpha-1}}.$$

Suppose

$$M_\alpha = \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n-\beta)^{\alpha-1}}.$$

From the proofs above, we have $d(u_i) = \delta$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, \beta$, $d(v_i) := \delta_1$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, (n - \beta)$, and $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e = \sum_{v \in V-I} d(v)$ which is the same as $e = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1$. Notice that $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e$ implies that there is no edge between any pair of vertices in $V - I$. Thus $V - I$ is independent.

Suppose G is a graph satisfying the following conditions. For any maximum independent set I in G , $d(u) = \delta$ if $u \in I$, $V - I$ is independent and $d(v) = \delta_1 \geq \delta$ if $v \in V - I$, and $e = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} M_\alpha &= \sum_{u \in I} d^\alpha(u) + \sum_{v \in V-I} d^\alpha(v) = \beta\delta^\alpha + (n - \beta)\delta_1^\alpha \\ &= \beta\delta^\alpha + (n - \beta) \left(\frac{\beta\delta}{n - \beta}\right)^\alpha = \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - \beta)^{\alpha-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proofs of Theorem 1.

References

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